

Spectrophotometric Study of Nickel Complex with Thiovioluric Acid

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It has been found that when an aqueous solution of thiovioluric acid (HTVA) is added to a nickel salt solution and pH is raised by addition of sodium hydroxide, a yellow colour appears due to the formation of nickel complex. Investigations on this colour reaction have been carried out spectrophotometrically and its suitability for determination of nickel has been examined.

Experimental

HTVA was synthesised by the method of Lal and Dutt¹. Freshly prepared solution of the reagent was used. Nickel nitrate was used for analar (BDH) sample while reagent grade chemicals were used for interference studies.

A Unicam spectrophotometer, SP 600, was used for taking absorbance readings. Measurements of pH were carried out on a Metrohm- pH-meter, E-350. Dilute solutions of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid were employed for adjusting pH's.

Recommended procedure for determination of nickel (II)

To a suitable aliquot containing between 5.63 and 26.29 μg of nickel (II) is added an excess of thiovioluric acid in aqueous solution. The pH is adjusted between 8.05–9.1 and volume is made up with water. The absorbance of the solution is measured at 375 nm against a reagent blank prepared under similar conditions. The amount of nickel (II) is then deduced from the calibration curve.

Physico-chemical constants

The system was found to adhere to Beer's law up to 3.05 ppm of nickel. The optimum concentration range at the same pH for accurate determination of nickel, as deduced from Ringbom plot², has been found to be 0.56–2.63 ppm of nickel. The sensitivity expressed in terms of Sandell's definition, comes out to be 0.0025 $\mu\text{g Ni/cm}^2$ for $\log I_0/I = 0.001$. The molar absorptivity is 2.33×10^4 .

Stoichiometry of the complex

Molar composition of the complex was determined by Job's method of continuous variations³.

Job's method at pH 8.5

For this purpose, a series of solutions were prepared in which mole fraction of nickel and that of thiovioluric acid was varied, keeping the total molarity constant. Nickel and thiovioluric acid solutions of

the same molarity were used. On plotting it was seen that at maximum absorbance, mole fraction of nickel was 0.33, which indicated the formation of a 1 : 2 complex.

The conclusion reached by the mole ratio method is in agreement with the results obtained by the application of Job's method.

Effect of diverse ions

To study the effect of foreign ions, synthetic solutions containing known amounts of nickel together with diverse ions were prepared and nickel was determined in their presence. Using 1.878 ppm of nickel, the following foreign ions did not interfere (amounts shown in parentheses): acetate (100), bromide (20), iodide (20), borate (100), oxalate (20), sulphate (100), thiocyanate (20), nitrate (100), nitrite (50), sulphite (50), and chloride (50). But pyrophosphate, tartrate, citrate, thiourea and phosphate interfere seriously. EDTA and NTA prevent the formation of colour. Magnesium (5), molybdenum (10), tungsten (50), manganese (10), tellurium (5), selenium (10), thallium (10), calcium (10), strontium (10) and barium (10) did not interfere. But some of the cations such as cobalt, iron, copper, palladium, rhodium (II), platinum (IV) and ruthenium (III) interfere seriously due to the fact that they develop their own colours. The use of masking agents was also made but attempts to mask these cations were unsuccessful.

The above results reveal that the method is not very selective like the other known methods for the purpose.

Conclusion

Several reagents have been suggested for spectrophotometric determination of nickel. The chelating agents which are generally used for the purpose are dimethylglyoxime⁴, nioxime⁵, furildioxime⁴ and diethyldithiocarbamate⁴. Diethyldithio-carbamate⁴ method is not at all selective and prior separation of nickel from interfering ions is necessary. But, 2,3-quinoxalinedithiol and dithiooxamide⁶ are quite useful reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of nickel. As compared to most of the other reagents, HTVA is also not a selective reagent and prior separation of interfering ions is necessary.

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